

Efficient metrics for the detection of partial discharges under steep-fronted voltage pulses

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Abstract

The increasing use of power electronic inverters in electrical drives is leading to the unexpected inception of partial discharges (PD) within the insulation system of electric machine stator windings. Unfortunately, the short rise and fall times of such voltages, below 100 nanoseconds in most cases, create high-magnitude conducted and radiated interferences that affect the measurements. Detecting partial discharges in these systems with inductive or electromagnetic sensors turns to be an important challenge, especially when interference and partial discharges share the same bandwidth. In this work, the authors propose a technique to detect the occurrence of PD in such systems, even when they are masked by disturbances. The proposed technique combines an analog high-pass filter stage and a digital band-pass to select a proper spectral interval. The resulting signal is converted to the base-band, where two metrics based on the peak-to-average power ratio are proposed. Experimental results obtained with the signals acquired with two antennas show that both proposed metrics exhibit a significant increase, about ten times greater, when the applied voltage exceeds the PD inception voltage. These contributions define new markers for the detection of PD events created by pulsed voltages with overlapped overshoots with promising results.

Keywords: Electric vehicles, radio-frequency sensors, partial discharges, spectral analysis, electrical insulation, electric motors, inverters

1. Introduction

Traditionally, simple speed and torque control have been the main advantages of DC motors. With the development of power electronics, inexpensive and robust brushless AC electric motors have rendered their DC relatives almost to oblivion in new designs. The use of the pulse width modulation (PWM) technique to create waveforms with variable frequency is possible thanks to high-voltage derivatives, which reduces commutation losses in the inverter and the machine [1]. The use of these speed-regulated motors is living a new blooming reboot thanks to the soaring industry of electric vehicles.

Unfortunately, these steep-fronted pulses are prone to lead to unexpected failures in the stator insulation of these synchronous and asynchronous machines [1, 2, 3]. It has been reported that these problems are a consequence of two specific circumstances: on the one hand, the overvoltages created by the impedance mismatch between the cable from the inverter to the motor and the motor itself [4]; on the other hand, the uneven voltage distribution along random wound coils [5]. This means that transient voltages well above the rated voltage are being applied between two magnet wires whose insulation (epoxy-based enamel) was not designed for these stresses [1, 5]. The consequence of these overvoltages is the appearance of low-energy ionization processes known as partial discharges (PD) that can take place in all types of insulating materials [6, 7, 8] and, eventually, provoke a total breakdown of the electric machine.

In the case of motor windings, previous works reveal that voltages around 500 V can ignite partial discharges in the small air wedges between magnet wires with few microns of enamel

[9]. The result of the ionization is the impact of accelerated electrons in the enamel which lead to physical and chemical attack of the solid insulation which, in the long term, creates short-circuits between wires and the consequent complete destruction of the coil [5]. In the literature, turn to turn PD have been identified as the main cause of stator insulation failures in inverter-fed drives [1, 10]. Thus, the detection and measurement of PD have become a necessity for the monitoring of inverter-fed AC motors, helping to obtain promising results in terms of diagnosis and predictive maintenance [11].

The standardized PD measurement procedure is based on instrumentation systems with bandwidth reaching 500 kHz using capacitive dividers to lower the high-voltage applied to the insulation. Another standardized possibility is the use of high-frequency current transformers, HFCT, with bandwidths of tens of MHz [12]. Both methods can provide useful information even in on-line measurements [13]. However, when power inverters feed electric motors, the detection of PD is a great challenge since the high voltage derivative values induce interference signals in the instrumentation systems up to hundreds of MHz, hindering the identification of the phenomenon with existing conventional methods and commercial solutions, [14]. In [15], the PD detection is accomplished through RC circuits tuned to create resonance when connected to a coaxial cable, which leads to high noise levels (above 5 Vpp); the latter is solved by means of a time-domain filtering through subtraction of signals from a time-moving average from the signals. The system is able to detect PD, but the thresholds to set an alarm for PD appearance are not clear and the hardware circuit

behavior could change for its application in an inductive test object. Another recent study detected PD on multi-level inverters but using a detection circuit which requires galvanic contact with the equipment under test [16]. In [17], the authors use as a sensor a monopole in contact with the power cable to detect PD by capacitive coupling; denoising is made by wavelet transform with an automatic selection of the filtering parameters with good results.

Some previous attempts to detect PDs under impulsive voltages have restricted the study to rise times above $3\ \mu\text{s}$ [18] whereas conventional IGBT-based inverters show values quite below 200 ns. Moreover, the use of new power electronic devices based on SiC and GaN can reduce these rise times below 100 ns [2, 19, 20]. Some works have detected PD successfully for voltage with rise time around 100 ns using antennas in the UHF range with hardware high-pass filters (HPF) to damp conducted and radiated interference [21, 22, 23]. The selection of the appropriate antenna and the cutoff frequency are critical in the detection, which has been the focus of many recent studies. In [24], the authors use a monopole antenna placed very close to the twisted pair sample to detect the radiation of the partial discharge. A similar device, this time using a spherical antenna is presented in [25]. In [23, 20, 26, 27] the selected sensors in the detection of PD in inverter-fed motors are circular polarized Archimedes antennas tuned to the same band of frequencies in which we find the phenomenon. The use of antennas has become a good option for PD detection in not-shielded high-voltage equipment since it allows making PD detection on-line without decommissioning the electric asset [28].

However, the wide variety of power electronic devices, geometries and shielding characteristics from motors and radiated/conducted bandwidths from different types of PD make it impossible to get a universal solution only through hardware. Indeed, the great difficulty to detect the phenomenon with high accuracy led to a multi-sensor approach in [29], where optical and UHF sensors are simultaneously used to check the appearance of PD.

There are many signal processing techniques applied to the extraction of PD from noisy signals [30]. Unfortunately, the detection of PD is especially difficult in signals with superimposed impulsive transients [31]. Recently, [32] presented a new development where changes in standard deviation of the acquired signal in the time domain were used to detect the discharges. Authors in [33] used the frequency-domain standard deviation of the signals to choose the appropriate frequency intervals for noise rejection by means of the spectral power ratios technique. In [34], the inventors proposed a device with different resolution bandwidths for receiving broad-band impulse signals, improving the detection of PD.

In this paper, the approach is using an instrumentation system that avoids galvanic contact to the test object, and applies new signal processing techniques and markers which can give clear thresholds for PD detection. The latter is the main contribution to the state of the art, since this could help in PD identification for non specialists in this field or even for future unsupervised systems. PDs are measured with two types of antennas with different frequency responses and bandwidths, and a new process-

Figure 1: Schematic explaining the experimental setup. A high DC voltage is switched to generate a square wave that is applied to a twisted pair simulating a motor random winding of an electric vehicle. The applied voltage and the radiation are acquired with an oscilloscope and stored to be processed offline.

ing technique for the detection of PD overlapped and hidden in steep voltage flanks is presented. The applied voltages (AV) are not pure square-wave voltages as in many previous papers, but they are transients with an overshoot as those present in electric vehicles due to the fact that they have inverter-fed drives with long feeding cables.

The proposed technique to detect PD is based on finding and processing those spectral components of PD that are not masked by the applied voltage transient. These components are filtered and down-mixed to the base-band using two alternative techniques: one based on the envelope calculation, and the other based on the energy in a time-limited window. It is shown that the peak-to-average value of the resulting base-band signals can be used as metrics to detect whether PD were present or not in the acquired signal. Two different metrics based on these peak-to-average values are presented: the peak-to-average power ratio (PAPR) and the completely new peak-dispersion-to-average power ratio (PDAPR). Their performance will be compared to provide new signal processing solutions for the detection of PD created by voltages with high du/dt values. The experimental results obtained with two types of antennas, confirm that the proposed metrics are valid for sensors that exhibit different frequency responses. Moreover, the use of five different applied voltages shows how the metrics exhibit a significant increment when the PD inception voltage is exceeded.

This paper is organized in four additional sections. Section II describes the experimental setup. The proposed technique to detect PD is presented in Section III. Experimental results are shown and discussed in Section IV. Finally, in Section V some conclusions are drawn.

2. Experimental setup

Figure 1 shows an outline of the experimental setup. The pulsed voltages were created with a circuit based on a HTS 91-01-HB-C switch driven by a square signal applied with a function generator. This power electronic device was used to obtain steep-fronted voltages with rise times between 30 ns and 50 ns, and amplitudes up to 20 kV, though it was never necessary to

reach this value. The fundamental frequency of the squarewave was 1 kHz.

The usual test object to stress turn to turn insulation systems consists of a twisted pair of enameled wires to ensure a close contact between them [1, 9, 15, 24, 29]. In our tests, the wires were 0.6 mm in diameter with an insulation thickness of 18 μm .

The detection system used two types of antennas: a commercial log-periodic antenna (UHALP 91088A), and a Vivaldi antenna tested to measure PD in [35]. The log-periodic has an almost flat frequency response between 300 MHz and 1.8 GHz with a gain between 6 and 7.6 dB according its specifications. The measured return losses were below -10 dB for the specified bandwidth. The Vivaldi antenna was designed to operate higher in a frequency centered around 2 GHz. The substrate is a FR4 dielectric with a thickness of 1.5 mm. In this case, the measured return losses are below -10 dB in the range between 1.5 GHz and 3.7 GHz though PD in enamel wires are found below 1.5 GHz. The Vivaldi antenna gain is between 4.5 dB and 6.8 dB according to the simulations performed beforehand. The total size of the antenna is approximately 9×12 cm. This Vivaldi antenna has been selected with the intention of using a sensor not tuned to the frequencies of interest, and testing the detection algorithm in unfavourable conditions. On the contrary, the log-periodic antenna is able to acquire all radiated frequency domain components from the PD physical phenomenon, but presents as a clear drawback its bigger sensitivity to noise as well.

Both antennas were placed at a distance around 30 cm from the test sample. In a more realistic application such as shielded electric motors in vehicles (for off-line testing), the antennas should be pointing to the electromagnetic windows in the ventilation slots, for instance.

The applied voltage (AV) was measured using a high-voltage attenuating probe (with a reduction ratio of 1/1000) with a high bandwidth (up to 400 MHz), so voltage rise times as low as 1 ns can be accurately measured. Both the sensor and the probe were connected to two channels in a 20 GSps oscilloscope with a bandwidth of 1 GHz. The acquisition window was selected triggering the switch signal and ensuring that the rising and overshooting of these voltages are clearly seen.

The maximum applied voltage was limited to 1.5 kV, since previous measurements revealed that PD appeared above 1 kV [33]. One of the tests reached 1.8 kV and caused an immediate breakdown of the sample. Partial discharges are stochastic phenomena whose appearance and magnitude changes depend, not only on the applied voltage, but on environmental conditions and the availability of free electrons for ionization. Thus, this phenomenon is statistically characterized with 50 acquisitions for each of the following AV: 0.3 kV, 0.6 kV, 0.9 kV, 1.2 kV, and 1.5 kV [22, 33]. The selection of these voltages is important since we need to ensure that there are measurements without and with partial discharges to determine their frequency band. Therefore, the AV ranges from values clearly below the PD inception voltage (PDIV) and values well above the inception voltage such as 1.5 kV.

Figure 2: Proposed processing chain to detect PD. HPF is an analog high-pass filter. BPF is a digital band-pass filter. Signal $x_f(t)$ is shifted to the base-band, resulting $x_e(t)$ and $x_w(t)$.

3. Proposed technique

Figure 2 shows the proposed technique to detect PD. The antenna signal $x_a(t)$ is processed by a high-pass filter (HPF). The resulting $x_m(t)$ is analog-to-digital converted, band-pass filtered, and mixed to the base-band through two alternative techniques. The resulting base-band signals $x_e(t)$ and $x_w(t)$, envelope and energy in a moving window, respectively, feed the detection metrics algorithms. The following subsections go through the technique in detail.

3.1. High-pass filter (HPF)

The first block shown in Figure 2 is a high-pass filter (HPF) that reduces those frequency components, both radiated and conducted, whose main source is the applied voltage. These components, that present high amplitude at the lower parts of the spectrum, must be filtered out before converting the signal to digital. Otherwise, weak high-frequency variations owing to PD would be masked by the quantization noise as a result of the analog-to-digital conversion. Notice that, even with the HPF, the low frequency components are too energetic and they are not completely blocked.

For the sake of simplicity, the AV signal can be modeled as a trapezoidal periodic waveform with 50% duty-cycle, rise-time t_r , and fundamental frequency f_c . Thus, its magnitude spectrum envelope decreases -20 dB/dec in the interval $[f_1, f_2]$, and -40 dB/dec for $f > f_2$, where $f_1 = (2f_c/\pi)$, and $f_2 = (\pi t_r)^{-1}$ [36]. For example: considering $f_1 = 10$ kHz (fundamental frequency $f_c = 15.7$ kHz) and $f_2 = 10$ MHz (rise-time $t_r = 31.8$ ns), the spectral envelope of a 1 kV AV will exhibit values of 1 V, 10 mV, and 100 μV at 10 MHz, 100 MHz, and 1 GHz, respectively. A proper value for the cut-off frequency of an ideal HPF is one decade above f_2 . Thus, the remaining AV components are comparable to the components of PD.

For real HPF implementations, the cut-off frequency should be increased to guarantee that the low frequency components are highly attenuated. The HPF used in our test setup is an LC coaxial filter with a 245 MHz cut-off frequency (about three times the recommended value for the ideal filter). This filter presents -40 dB attenuation from DC to 145 MHz, -20 dB from 145 MHz to 190 MHz, and a pass-band from 290 MHz to 3 GHz with losses below 1.5 dB.

Figure 3: Power spectral density (PSD) versus frequency (ordinate) and time (abscissa) for: (a) AV=900 V Vivaldi antenna, (b) AV=1500 V Vivaldi antenna, (c) AV=900 V Vivaldi antenna with HPF, (d) AV=1500 V Vivaldi antenna with HPF, (e) AV=900 V log-periodic antenna with HPF, and (f) AV=1500 V log-periodic antenna with HPF. Dashed-line located in 300 MHz (HPF cut-off frequency).

(a)

(b)

Figure 4: Mean value of the PSD: (a) signals captured by the Vivaldi antenna, and (b) log-periodic antenna.

To illustrate the effects of the HPF, Figure 3 shows the time-frequency diagrams (i.e., spectrograms) of signals measured with the previously described Vivaldi and log-periodic antennas. Frames were captured using a sampling frequency $F_s = 20$ GSps. A repetitive pulse applied voltage source with a rise-time $t_r \approx 40$ ns was used ($f_1 \approx 636$ Hz, and $f_2 \approx 8$ MHz). The maximum AV was 0.9 kV in subplots of the left column, remaining below the PDIV, and 1.5 kV in subplots in the right column, that clearly exceeds the PDIV. In subplots from (a) to (d) the signal was captured by a Vivaldi antenna, whereas in (e) and (f) it was used a log-periodic. In the last two rows a hardware implementation of the HPF was used (the cut-off frequency is drawn in dashed lines). As preliminary measurements revealed, the log-periodic antenna detects a strong interference from the pulsed voltage which saturated the oscilloscope channel [33], so these spectrograms are not shown.

The spectrograms of Figure 3 evidence that: 1) we find intense frequency components owing to the AV in the lower part of the spectrum, up to 600 MHz; 2) when the PDIV is exceeded, some high frequency intervals exhibit more intense values; 3) in this case, the high frequency components due to PD are more visible when the HPF is installed.

3.2. Band-pass filter (BPF)

PDs are extremely narrow in the time domain, resulting a broadband signal in the frequency domain. Considering a simple Gaussian function to model a PD pulse, it will exhibit a bandwidth in the frequency domain $B_{pd} = 0.88/\tau_{pd}$ for a given pulse-width τ_{pd} in the time-domain, where both, B_{pd} and

Table 1: BPF configurations for Vivaldi and log-periodic antennas.

Id.	Vivaldi		log-periodic	
	f_c (GHz)	B_c (MHz)	f_c (GHz)	B_c (MHz)
#0	BPF bypassed		BPF bypassed	
#1	0.67	150	0.87	100
#2	1.63	100	1.10	200
#3	1.75	100	1.51	150
#4	1.84	150	1.86	100

τ_{pd} , are measured in the full-width at the half-maximum sense. Thus, those PDs whose widths in the time domain are in the range of sub-nanoseconds, extend their bandwidth in the frequency domain in the range of GHz [35]. These components are radiated in the neighborhood, and some of them are masked by the commutation disturbance due to the applied voltage, mainly in the lower part of the spectrum [22].

PD signals share the spectrum with other radio communication services that use the so-called ultra-high frequency (UHF) band. It has been observed stationary and intense components at 1.675 GHz (satellite mobile service, used in aeronautics as meteorological aids), at 932 MHz (radio-location services), and at 806 MHz (radio-broadcast services) [28].

The BPF of Figure 2 selects the spectral interval where PD spectral components are significant, and rejects those components owing to deterministic sources, including the interference due to the applied voltage. A finite impulse response (FIR) filter has been selected with Gaussian magnitude response, centered at f_c , and bandwidth B_c .

To find proper values for the BPF center frequency and bandwidth, a frequency analysis of the captured signals must be performed. Figure 4 shows the mean value of the power spectral density (PSD) of 50 signals captured with the two previously described antennas for three applied voltages: two of them below the PDIV (300 V, 600 V), and one above (1200 V). The PSD of the first two AV are very similar, and can be used to reject some intervals where the radio-frequency services are present. For AV= 1200 V, the PDIV is exceeded, and PD are responsible for some spectral components to increase in some intervals whose location also depends on the frequency response of each antenna. Those intervals are selected as those where the increase is more than 3 dB in a wide enough width (e.g., greater than 50 MHz). We have selected four configurations for each antenna, detailed in Table 1. In the log-periodic antenna there are more suitable intervals, which is expected from the flatter response of this commercial device.

The effects of the BPF are illustrated in Figure 5 for two applied voltages, where the measured signal, the applied voltage, and the band-pass filtered signal $x_f(t)$ are drawn. The label “PD” indicates the time interval where the PD activity has been observed. (c) and (d) plots are obtained for the Vivaldi antenna using the configuration of the BPF labeled as #1 in Table 1. When the applied voltage remains below the PDIV, $x_f(t)$ presents low amplitude (with maxima in 0.7 mV), but when the PDIV is reached, the maximum amplitude of $x_f(t)$ increases dramatically up to 13.7 mV, showing that there is PD activity hidden in the signal received by the antenna.

Figure 5: Applied voltage, measured signal $x_m(t)$, band-pass filtered signal $x_f(t)$, and base-band signals $x_e(t)$ and $x_w(t)$. In (b) and (d) the applied voltage exceeds the PDIV, whereas in (a) and (c) no PD activity was observed. Setup: Vivaldi antenna, BPF configuration #1, time window $W = 10$ ns.

Figure 6: Applied voltage where the base-band signals ('x' for the envelope, and 'o' for the windowed-energy) reach their maxima. The AV reaches 1.2 kV (light green), and 1.5 kV (light blue).

3.3. Base-band signals

A measure of the strength of the band-pass filtered signal $x_f(t)$ can be used to track whether PD are present or not in the recorded frame. We propose two alternatives to measure the signal strength of such a band-pass signal: the envelope $x_e(t)$, and the energy in a moving time-limited window of W seconds, $x_w(t)$. These two base-band signals are computed as shown in (1) and (2), where \mathcal{H} denotes the Hilbert transform.

$$x_e(t) = |\mathcal{H}[x_f(t)]|, \quad (1)$$

where:

$$\mathcal{H}[(t)] = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{x_f(\tau)}{t - \tau} d\tau$$

$$x_w(t) = \int_{t-W/2}^{t+W/2} x_f^2(\tau) d\tau \quad (2)$$

In this paper, the envelope of the band-pass signal is extracted by using the magnitude of the analytic signal provided by the Hilbert transform [37]. This method has been chosen because it is simple for off-line computation and does not distort the resulting envelope, but it is computationally intensive for real-time applications. An alternative for such applications is the well-known envelope detector as shown in [26] or its digital implementation used in [38]. The windowed-energy signal $x_w(t)$ is also simpler to compute but requires an additional parameter W , that must be wider than the PD width.

Figure 5 (c) and (d) show the envelope signal $x_e(t)$ and the windowed-energy signal $x_w(t)$ (with $W = 10$ ns) for two AVs: 0.9 kV and 1.5 kV. Both signals exhibit a significant amplitude increment in presence of PD (maximum AV of 1.5 kV). It has to be noted that these base-band signals are insensitive to the commutation disturbance.

Figure 6 is a very illustrative graphic where the fifty PDs are represented in the time domain over the applied voltages at 1.5 kV (light blue), and 1.2 kV (light green). It can be observed

that most of the PDs are generated around 1.2 kV of the instantaneous voltage.

3.4. Proposed detection metrics

The peak-to-average power ratio (PAPR) of a signal is a well-known parameter to show how extreme the peaks are in a waveform, therefore, we propose using the PAPR of the base-band signals to detect PDs, and reject noise and interference. A PAPR about 0 dB indicates no peak, i.e., no PD, whereas an eventual PD would produce a high PAPR value.

Expressions (3) and (4) show the proposed PAPR metrics to detect PD, for the envelope and the windowed-energy signals, respectively. In (3), $x_{e,peak}$ and $x_{e,rms}$ are the peak and the RMS values of the envelope $x_e(t)$, respectively. For the equivalent PAPR definition of the windowed-energy signal, shown in (4), $x_{w,peak}$ is the peak and $x_{w,mean}$ is mean value of signal $x_w(t)$. Both metrics, that will be expressed in dB, must be computed in a time window around the positive edge of the AV where PDs are prone to happen as the inception voltage has been surpassed.

$$PAPR_e = x_{e,peak}^2 / x_{e,rms}^2 \quad (3)$$

$$PAPR_w = x_{w,peak} / x_{w,mean} \quad (4)$$

Whenever a partial discharge occurs, it is expected to find a high peak value in any of the base-band signals. For the example shown in Figure 5, the resulting PAPRs for a maximum AV of 0.9 kV were: $PAPR_e = 7.9$ (9 dB) and $PAPR_w = 4.5$ (6.5 dB). When the PDIV was exceeded (maximum AV of 1.5 kV) the proposed metrics increase to $PAPR_e = 137.3$ (21.4 dB) and $PAPR_w = 97.5$ (19.9 dB).

Figure 7 shows the histograms of the proposed metrics for four applied voltages increasing from top to bottom were the abscissa represents the value for the PAPR and the ordinate the number of events. The histograms for the Vivaldi and the log-periodic antenna are shown in the first and second columns, respectively. The mean and standard deviation values of the PAPRs are included in the legends (also in dB). The four histograms on the top, measured for two AVs lower than the PDIV, show lower mean values for both metrics (about 9 dB for $PAPR_e$ and 7 dB for $PAPR_w$). The mean value of the PAPRs increase about 10 dB when the AV exceeds the PDIV (1.2 kV and 1.5 kV), as shown in the two last rows of Figure 7. Moreover, the mean value of the PAPR metrics also exhibits an increment of about 2.5 dB when comparing the 1.2 kV to 1.5 kV applied voltage, showing that the PDs generated in the latter are stronger.

Due to the random nature of the PD [32], the proposed metrics $PAPR_e$ and $PAPR_w$ also exhibit greater dispersion when the AV exceeds the PDIV. For example: for the Vivaldi antenna and the windowed-energy, the standard deviation of $PAPR_w$ increased from -0.9 dB, for an AV of 0.9 kV, to 13.7 dB and 13.9 dB, when the AV increased to 1.2 kV and 1.5 kV, respectively.

The reason of the observed dispersion in the PAPR value is found in the dispersion of the magnitude of the PD peak values. The peak values obtained when the AV reaches the PDIV

are not only greater but also more dispersed which precisely is consistent with the stochastic nature of the partial discharges. Thus, an additional metric to detect PDs is proposed in (5) and (6), where PDAPR stands for the peak-dispersion-to-average power ratio, and the subscripts refer to the base-band signal. Operators $Var[\cdot]$ and $Std[\cdot]$ stand for the variance and standard deviation values, respectively.

$$PDAPR_e = Var[x_{e,peak}] / E[x_{e,rms}^2] \quad (5)$$

$$PDAPR_w = Std[x_{w,peak}] / E[x_{w,mean}] \quad (6)$$

For the results shown in Figure 7, the proposed PDAPRs metrics exhibit a very low value when the PDIV is not exceeded. For example: $PDAPR_e$ was as low as -10.9 dB for the Vivaldi antenna for AV=0.9 kV, and it increased up to 10.4 dB and 12.5 dB for AV= 1.2 kV and AV= 1.5 kV, respectively.

4. Discussion

The proposed PAPR and PDAPR metrics have been measured for two antennas, four BPF configurations detailed in Table 1, and five applied voltages (two of them above the PD inception voltage). Table 2 and Table 3 show the results for the Vivaldi and log-periodic antenna, respectively. The following analysis can be done.

The PAPR metrics exhibit a significant increment (in the worst case: 7.7 dB for $PDAPR_e$, and 9.8 dB for $PDAPR_e$) when the applied voltage exceeds the PDIV, regardless of the configuration used (antenna base-band signal or spectral interval), except for configuration #4 using the log-periodic antenna.

Configuration #4 in the log-periodic antenna has been intentionally included to illustrate that, even though the spectral components due to PD and interference share the same spectral interval, the proposed PDAPR metrics are able to detect the presence of PD. In this configuration, there is an interference (see the spectrogram of Figure 3(c) and the PSD of Figure 4(b)), that makes the base-band signals to exhibit some peaks in the time domain, increasing the resulting PAPR value. However, the deterministic nature of these peaks owing to interference reduces the PDAPR value. As a result, the PDAPR metrics increase 14 dB and 10 dB for the envelope and the windowed-energy base-band signals, respectively, when the PDIV is exceeded.

Both PAPR and PDAPR metrics present an approximated constant value for the three lower applied voltages, and increasing values for the AP that exceed the PDIV.

Concerning the proposed PDAPR metrics, the observed increments when PDs are present are even greater than those shown by the PAPR metrics. The values obtained for both, $PDAPR_e$ and $PDAPR_w$, depend on the selected antenna, spectral interval, and the base-band signal. In any case, these changes in response do not compromise PD detection, since the changes in dB are much larger once PDs appear.

Finally, the results of configuration #0 show the relevance of using the proposed BPF. In this configuration, PDs can be clearly detected for the most extreme case (i.e., AV= 1.5 kV)

Figure 7: $PAPR_e$ and $PAPR_w$ histograms. Vivaldi antenna in column (a). Log-periodic in column (b). Legends include their mean and standard deviation values ($E[\cdot]/Std[\cdot]$). Values in parenthesis in dB. 50 captures per test. $W = 10$ ns, filter configuration #1 (see Table 1). Label “*” indicates that the AV exceeds the PDIV.

Table 2: Results for Vivaldi antenna. Mean value of PAPR / PDAPR in dB for both proposed metrics.

Envelope					
AV	#0	#1	#2	#3	#4
0.3 kV	15.0/-14.5	9.1/-11.3	8.9/-10.5	8.7/-10.4	9.5/-11.4
0.6 kV	14.9/-17.6	9.0/-12.4	8.6/-9.9	8.7/-7.8	9.2/-9.9
0.9 kV	14.7/-18.4	9.0/-10.9	8.9/-11.0	8.9/-10.2	9.2/-10.4
1.2 kV	15.7/-10.5	18.3/10.4	17.6/10.0	16.9/6.2	18.7/10.3
1.5 kV	14.9/-8.1	21.4/12.5	21.4/12.0	21.0/11.5	22.1/13.1

Windowed-energy:					
AV	#0	#1	#2	#3	#4
0.3 kV	12.9/-2.3	6.8/0.3	6.7/0.0	6.8/0.6	6.5/-0.6
0.6 kV	13.8/-2.2	6.7/-0.1	6.6/0.8	6.8/1.6	6.2/-1.4
0.9 kV	14.1/-2.6	6.5/-0.6	6.7/0.2	6.9/0.4	6.5/-1.2
1.2 kV	14.3/0.8	16.9/17.0	15.9/15.8	14.2/12.0	16.6/16.4
1.5 kV	14.2/2.1	19.9/18.7	19.7/18.9	18.1/16.8	19.9/18.8

Table 3: Results for Log-periodic antenna. Mean value of PAPR / PDAPR in dB for both proposed metrics.

Envelope:					
AV	#0	#1	#2	#3	#4
0.3 kV	21.2/-12.1	8.9/-8.3	9.2/-10.3	8.8/-10.4	18.3/-5.1
0.6 kV	19.6/-10.6	8.9/-8.7	9.1/-10.4	8.9/-12.1	14.3/-7.1
0.9 kV	18.1/-12.2	9.3/-5.5	9.1/-11.4	8.8/-12.7	16.2/-4.4
1.2 kV	18.5/-12.4	17.0/6.6	19.1/8.8	18.3/7.2	18.0/10.9
1.5 kV	20.0/8.5	19.5/12.7	22.0/12.5	21.3/11.7	19.4/12.9

Windowed-energy:					
AV	#0	#1	#2	#3	#4
0.3 kV	15.7/-2.8	6.6/0.6	5.6/-2.1	6.0/-0.5	16.6/7.7
0.6 kV	14.6/-2.7	6.6/0.9	5.5/-0.3	5.9/-1.5	12.7/4.9
0.9 kV	13.5/-4.0	7.1/2.6	5.6/-1.5	6.1/-1.4	14.9/7.2
1.2 kV	13.9/-3.0	15.1/13.3	15.7/13.1	15.6/13.4	16.8/17
1.5 kV	14.2/13.1	17.5/17.3	18.8/17.3	18.4/17.3	18.3/19.4

using the PDAPR metric with the log-periodic antenna. With the Vivaldi antenna, PDAPR evidences the presence of PDs for AV= 1.2 kV, but the increment observed in the metric is considerably reduced when compared to the other configurations. If the BPF is bypassed, the PAPR metric is unable to detect PDs.

5. Conclusions

This paper shows that important fast voltage surges can happen in electric motors driven by inverters. Although these steep fronted voltages do not provoke an immediate breakdown, they do facilitate the appearance of partial discharges that would eventually undermine the insulation with serious consequences. This is especially alarming in the electric vehicle industry, and manufacturers are concerned with the need of detecting partial discharges. However, this is not an easy task since PDs manifest as fast current pulses precisely when the voltage surge happens and propagate through the wires with a similar bandwidth as the voltage pulse. This paper proposes the isolation of PD signals with a technique based on a series of HPF and BPF that extracts the information of interest from the rising pulse interference. Two metrics are proposed to automatically detect variations in the base band. The peak-to-average power ratio (PAPR) shows that there is a concentration of power in the frequency bands of interest. Since this power can be due to interference, the metric is complemented with the peak-dispersion-to-average power ratio PDAPR that explains the variance of the peak in the base band referred to the average. A large value of this peak shows that the signal in that narrow frequency band is stochastic and the origin is due to a partial discharge more than a radio interference. The proposed processing technique has been proved to work successfully with real signals from a twisted pair simulating a random winding in an electric motor. Experimental results show that the proposed metrics exhibit a significant increment when PDs are present, an increment that is not shown for simple filtered signals. PAPR have shown good results in the past for PD detection in these noisy environments, but PDAPR shows larger increases in dB for voltages above PDIV, which points to

a new promising marker for PD detection in inverter-fed drives

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